

eDNAqua-Plan

Blueprint

workshop

Oct 8-9, 2025

eDNAqua-Plan

NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Day 1. Wednesday, October 8 2025

14:00 - 18:00 CEST, online

14:00 - 14:20	About eDNAqua-Plan Nicolas Page (EMBRC) What do we want to achieve with this workshop? Katrina Exter (VLIZ)
14:20 - 14:50	Mapping the eDNA data ecosystem: the Landscaping report Emilie Boulanger (UNESCO)
14:50 - 15:20	Plenary discussion time Your first thoughts on the current and future maps and the recommendations
15:20 - 15:35 15:35 - 15:45	Break Introduction to our Miro boards These will be used during the breakout sessions. Followed by a short break
15:45 - 16:30	Breakout session 1 Random assignment of attendees into three groups to each discuss different questions on the landscape and its recommendations and requirements
16:30 - 16:45 16:45 - 16:55	5 min summary of each breakout A summary of what each breakout has discussed Break
16:55 - 17:40	Breakout session 2 Random assignment again of attendees into three groups to each discuss different questions on the landscape and its recommendations and requirements
17:40 - 18:00	5 min summary of each breakout Summary of Day 1 and explanation of Day 2

<https://tinyurl.com/bdd7rvef>

PROJECT OVERVIEW

eDNAqua-Plan

NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Biodiversity monitoring

- Unleashing the power of biomonitoring and observation in aquatic environments
 - EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030
 - Convention on Biological Diversity

Lack of standards

- eDNA application is limited by the lack of standardized data formats and a consolidated data repository

Linking knowledge

- Information exchange and collaborative efforts using eDNA can happen with the appropriate tools and necessary standards

Goal

Producing a strategic blueprint and operational roadmap, with recommendations for community-wide structuring of the data handling aspect of future eDNA biomonitoring in Europe, and an implementation plan for how to achieve this in a sustainable way.

eDNAqua-Plan in numbers

- Almost 2 million of budget
 - (1 978 282.50 €)
- 18 partners from 11 countries
- 36 months

Making eDNA a
more robust
biomonitoring tool

Objectives

- Identification of related eDNA/DNA aquatic monitoring efforts
 - Collect information on existing projects, Initiatives and infrastructures for aquatic monitoring in the EU and associated countries
- Harmonized and Standardized Data Infrastructure
 - Provide an overview of all national and international activities of standardization and interoperability of methods and data workflows
- Integrated Reference Library
 - Assess the relevance and feasibility of the creation of a digital ecosystem of eDNA repositories
 - Propose an integrated and dynamic reference library of marine and freshwater species that is open-access and based on FAIR principles to support future aquatic biodiversity monitoring programmes and mapping initiatives

eDNAqua-Plan implementation

Work Packages

Work Package 1

Management, communication & stakeholder engagement

Lead: EMBRC-ERIC

Work Package 2

Audit and gap analysis

Lead: ULOD

Work Package 3

Data standards, data linking & compatibility

Lead: UNESCO

Work Package 4

Use cases: Testing the developed eDNA library infrastructure

Lead: EV ILVO

Work Package 5

Blueprint, roadmap and sustainability

Lead: SSBE

Today's outcomes

- Comprehensive landscape audit
 - Completed a gap analysis of over 60 eDNA initiatives and 850 scientific publications; mapped workflows and data repositories across Europe
- Testing in Real-World Use Cases
 - Assessed 22 marine and freshwater datasets to validate data standards, workflows, and repository practices
- Data Standards & Interoperability
 - Defined essential metadata and curation practices; contributed to the development of a FAIR eDNA data ecosystem through collaborative workshops and stakeholder engagement

Today's outcomes

- **Blueprint & Roadmap Development**
 - Initiated strategic planning for a harmonised EU eDNA infrastructure, with stakeholder consultations and vision documents underway
- **Stakeholder & Policy Engagement**
 - Nearly 300 stakeholders identified; project presented at high-level events in Europe, North America, Asia, and South America
- **Open Science & Communication**
 - Project website launched with over 4,700 views; active presence on social media; publication of communication materials and a stakeholder Power BI dashboard

Thank you!

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 [@eDNAqua_plan](https://twitter.com/eDNAqua_plan)

 [eDNAqua-Plan](https://www.linkedin.com/company/eDNAqua-Plan)

 [@ednaquaplan](https://www.facebook.com/ednaquaplan)

What do we want to achieve in this workshop?

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**Funded by
the European Union**

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What do we want to achieve in this workshop?

Mapping the eDNA data ecosystem:

The eDNAqua-Plan landscape proposal

Emilie Boulanger, Katrina Exter, Joana Pauperio, Saara Suominen, Pieter Provoost, Frédéric Rimet, Antonio Picazo, Antonio Camacho, Camila Babo, Joana Verissimo, Veera Norros, Pascal Hablützel, Christina Pavloudi, Kristian Meissner, Peter Woollard

WP3: Data Standards, Data Linking, & Compatibility

WP2

Landscape analysis

Sep 2024

Reference Libraries and eDNA (workflow) gaps

WP4

Use cases

WP3

Discussions

Oct 2024

Workshop: discussion on standards requirements

Jan 2025

Workshop: conceptualise the eDNA landscape

Landscape proposal

Apr 2025

Detailed Doc

Recommendations

Feb 2026

Good Practice reports

- Reference libraries
- eDNA data standards
- Connectivity

WP4/5

WP4/5

Feedback

First, the current eDNA data landscape

First, the current eDNA data landscape

Caption

What works well

There are **plenty of places where one can publish**

- protocols (protocols.io, OBPS)
- software (GitHub-Zenodo, via software journals, WorkflowHub)
- sequence data (INSDC: ENA,NCBI, DDBJ) (raw and soon ASVs/OTUs)
- sampling metadata (BioSamples, BioProject) - INSDC use these
- biodiversity data derived from DNA (OBIS, GBIF etc)

There are already **good practices of publishing sequence data** alongside journal publications

There are **plenty of well-used standards and/or conventions**

- fasta and fastq
- MIxS (Minimum Information for any Sequence) and ENA/NCBI checklists for sequence data
- Darwin Core (DwC) and DwC-Archive for biodiversity data
- national and regional publishers that feed into OBIS/GBIF often provide excel templates (DwC)
- most provide metadata also in at least XML (machine-readable)

There are **plenty of metadata fields** available and **projects working on better practices** (FAIRe, BeBOP, ...)

What does not work well

The full ecosystem is complex and underused => *Lack of reusability and traceability/trustability of the data.*

Publishing (documents and data)

- Publication of specialist data in **generalist repositories** or just in **scientific articles**
- **Open Access publication of protocols** not yet standard practice
- **Biomonitoring data** are too often published in limited-access local/agency repositories

Metadata

- Most often **incomplete**: either fields are not filled in or not enough are mandatory.
- Information given in metadata is often **inaccessible**
- Often not **machine-understandable**

Standards (data and metadata)

- **Lack of guidance and consistency** as to which **standards** to use in metadata/data, how and where
- **Taxonomic identifications** in reference libraries and bioinformatics outputs can still lack PIDs/URL
- Insufficient mapping between taxonomic backbones/systems

Reference libraries

- Public databases contain gaps & errors, and the reliability of reference sequences is hard to evaluate
- Quality-controlled, taxonomically curated and thus reliable reference databases are sparse, often taxon-specific and lacking resources

From that, a proposal for the future

From that, a proposal for the future

data management plans

Overall:

- Benefit of the existing systems and structure
- Streamlining data flows
- Clear guidance on where to publish which data

Findable and reliable reference sequences

- Federated network of quality-controlled reference libraries
- Essential set of metadata
- Common taxonomic curation principles

All metadata standards are aligned to each other

Tools for finding, formatting and publishing

databases

Recommendations

A streamlined landscape, with some structural changes and recommendations for better practices

- Provide more **guidance** to data generators on where and how to submit their data.
- Provide more **tools** for scientists to use to format biodiversity and bioinformatics data
- Encourage **publishing pathways** from **local/thematic/national to regional/global**
- Encourage **diversity** of independent reference databases
- Focus on **machine-readable and -understandable** web standards
- Increase the number of, and frequency of, **mappings** between **vocabularies** and between **taxonomic backbones**
- Ensure these are **community-led efforts** for long term sustainability
- Samples: provide stricter and richer **provenance metadata** templates/fields
- **Encourage publishing** specialist data in the right repositories, incl. experimental and bioinformatics workflows
- Push our funders (funding agencies, universities) to **acknowledge data** as much as science publications
- As well as **providing** for the **resources** to allow sustainable practices that can adapt as the future comes

To look at these in detail

The landscape proposal and detailed diagrams, published to Zenodo

The screenshot shows a Zenodo record for 'eDNAqua-Plan Milestone 7: The eDNAqua-Plan conceptual landscape proposal v1'. It includes a search bar, user options (Log in, Sign up), and project statistics: 578 views and 643 downloads. The record is published on July 23, 2025, and is version v3. A list of contributors is provided, including Boulangier, Emilie; Exter, Katrina; Paupério, Joana; Suominen, Saara; Provoost, Pieter; Rimet, Frédéric; Picazo Mozo, Antonio; Camacho, Antonio; Babo, Camila; Verissimo, Joana; Norros, Veera; Hablitzel, Pascal; Pavlouli, Christina; Meissner, Kristian; Woollard, Peter. A 'Versions' table shows Version v3 (10.5281/zenodo.16367374) and Version v1 (10.5281/zenodo.16090825). A note at the bottom states: 'Cite all versions? You can cite all versions by using the DOI 10.5281/zenodo.16090824. This DOI represents all versions, and will always resolve to the latest one. Read more.'

The Miro workshop landing board

The workshop breakout sessions

Introduction to our Miro boards

Miro boards are like e-chalkboards that allow for real-time collaboration.

We have created a board for each breakout session – 1,2,3 for day 1; A, B, C for day 2

Each board has an area showing

- The future landscape
- The list of questions that we want to be addressed in the session, with a link to the reading material relevant for those questions
- An area for each question in which you will add your comments, thoughts, feedback as “post-its” aka “sticky notes”

The links to each Miro boards can be found in the README (Day 1 ... tab) in our google drive (<https://tinyurl.com/bdd7rvef>), the link to which was sent to you all over the weekend

Introduction to our DAY 1 Miro boards

ED eDNAqua-Plan
eDNAqua-Plan

Search by title or topic

Home

Recent

Starred

Pinned Spaces

Project Kick-off

Quickly access your most important Spaces by pinning them.

Spaces

Explore Miro

miro

Blank board

Goal Setting (OKR)

Roadmap

Blueprint

Boards in this team

Filter by All boards Owned by anyone...

Name

- Day 1 - Breakout session 1 Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3
- Day 1 - Breakout session 2 Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3
- Day 1 - Breakout session 3 Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3
- Day 2 - Breakout session A Modified by Peter Woollard, Oct 3
- Day 2 - Breakout session B Modified by Emilie Boulanger, Yesterday
- Welcome Board | Starter Plan Modified by Carlijn Kooie, Sep 9
- Workshop Landing Board** Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3

Time	Topic	Facilitator
14:00 - 14:30	Day 1 - Welcome, October 3 2023	14:00 - 14:30: Welcome
14:30 - 14:45	What do we want to achieve with this workshop? Katrina Exter (UEZ)	14:30 - 14:45: Welcome
14:45 - 15:00	Mapping the eDNA data landscape: the current landscape (Peter Woollard) (UEZ)	14:45 - 15:00: Welcome
15:00 - 15:15	Priority discussion: How far has progress on the current and future requirements and recommendations?	15:00 - 15:15: Welcome
15:15 - 15:30	Break	15:15 - 15:30: Welcome
15:30 - 15:45	Breakout session 1: Current landscape of eDNA data in the current landscape. Followed by a short break 10:15	15:30 - 15:45: Welcome
15:45 - 16:00	Breakout session 2: Current landscape of eDNA data in the current landscape. Followed by a short break 10:15	15:45 - 16:00: Welcome
16:00 - 16:15	Breakout session 3: Current landscape of eDNA data in the current landscape. Followed by a short break 10:15	16:00 - 16:15: Welcome
16:15 - 16:30	Breakout session 4: Current landscape of eDNA data in the current landscape. Followed by a short break 10:15	16:15 - 16:30: Welcome
16:30 - 16:45	Breakout session 5: Current landscape of eDNA data in the current landscape. Followed by a short break 10:15	16:30 - 16:45: Welcome
16:45 - 17:00	Breakout session 6: Current landscape of eDNA data in the current landscape. Followed by a short break 10:15	16:45 - 17:00: Welcome
17:00 - 17:15	Breakout session 7: Current landscape of eDNA data in the current landscape. Followed by a short break 10:15	17:00 - 17:15: Welcome
17:15 - 17:30	Breakout session 8: Current landscape of eDNA data in the current landscape. Followed by a short break 10:15	17:15 - 17:30: Welcome
17:30 - 17:45	Breakout session 9: Current landscape of eDNA data in the current landscape. Followed by a short break 10:15	17:30 - 17:45: Welcome
17:45 - 18:00	Breakout session 10: Current landscape of eDNA data in the current landscape. Followed by a short break 10:15	17:45 - 18:00: Welcome

How to get started

- Instructions for the workshop
- How to use miro**
 - We have prepared questions for each breakout session and landscape area or stakeholder.
 - You can answer these by adding sticky notes in each box - different coloured sticky notes can be used for different types of answers: see the offered examples
 - To practice: please add a sticky note with your name here in the participants box
 - In the breakout sessions**
 - Each breakout session, both for day 1 and day 2, have their dedicated boards
 - You can find the links to them here below in the breakout boxes
 - In each of these boards, you will find snapshots of the landscape with dedicated questions & room to answer with sticky notes
 - Any questions?**
 - Feel free to shout out your questions, rather than the zoom chat. It is acceptable to have live discussions during the breakouts
 - On day 1: we have dedicated health breaks
 - On day 2: take a health break whenever you want!

Introduction to our DAY 1 Miro boards

The screenshot displays the Miro workspace interface. On the left sidebar, the user is logged in as 'ED eDNAqua-Plan'. The sidebar includes a search bar, navigation options (Home, Recent, Starred), a 'Pinned Spaces' section with a 'Project Kick-off' card, and a 'Spaces' section with a '+ Add' button. The main area shows a list of boards under the heading 'Boards in this team'. The list includes:

- Day 1 - Breakout session 1 (Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3)
- Day 1 - Breakout session 2 (Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3)
- Day 1 - Breakout session 3 (Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3)
- Day 2 - Breakout session A (Modified by Peter Woollard, Oct 3)
- Day 2 - Breakout session B (Modified by Emilie Boulanger, Yesterday)
- Welcome Board | Starter Plan (Modified by Carlijn Koole, Sep 9)
- Workshop Landing Board (Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3)

The right side of the image shows a preview of a Miro board titled 'THE QUESTIONS' and 'THE LANDSCAPE'. The board contains several sticky notes and diagrams. A purple circle highlights the first three boards in the list, and a purple arrow points from this circle to the Miro board preview.

Introduction to our DAY 1 Miro boards

The image shows a Miro workspace interface. On the left is a navigation sidebar with sections: Home, Recent, Starred, Pinned Spaces (containing 'Project Kick-off'), and Spaces. The main area displays 'Boards in this team' with a list of boards. A purple circle highlights the first three 'Day 1 - Breakout session' boards. An arrow points from this circle to a larger, detailed view of the 'Day 1 - Breakout session 1' board. This board is titled 'THE QUESTIONS' and contains three main sections: 'THE QUESTIONS' (with a URL and three numbered questions), 'THE LANDSCAPE' (with a diagram), and 'Other comments'. A smaller inset shows a close-up of the 'Q2 How could we tackle these aspects?' section, which includes an example text box.

Navigation Sidebar:

- ED eDNAqua-Plan
- Search by title or topic
- Home
- Recent
- Starred
- Pinned Spaces: Project Kick-off
- Spaces: Explore Miro

Boards in this team:

- Day 1 - Breakout session 1 (Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3)
- Day 1 - Breakout session 2 (Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3)
- Day 1 - Breakout session 3 (Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3)
- Day 2 - Breakout session A (Modified by Peter Woollard, Oct 3)
- Day 2 - Breakout session B (Modified by Emilie Boulanger, Yesterday)
- Welcome Board | Starter Plan (Modified by Carlijn Koole, Sep 9)
- Workshop Landing Board (Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3)

THE QUESTIONS

See <https://tinyurl.com/yc3mau5m> for the "aspects of the current landscape" that these questions are about

Q1. Which aspects of the current landscape that do not work well do you dis/agree with and why?

Q2. How could we tackle these aspects?

Q3. Which recommendations are / are not a priority for your organisation to tackle; and why?

THE LANDSCAPE

Other comments

Q2 How could we tackle these aspects?

EXAMPLE: To have more open access publications of products if these were acknowledged as publications on a resume they are not likely to be published

Introduction to our DAY 1 Miro boards

The image shows a screenshot of the Miro workspace interface. On the left, the navigation sidebar includes sections for 'Home', 'Recent', 'Starred', 'Pinned Spaces' (with a 'Project Kick-off' item), and 'Spaces'. The main area displays 'Boards in this team' with a list of boards including 'Day 1 - Breakout session 1', 'Day 1 - Breakout session 2', 'Day 1 - Breakout session 3', 'Day 2 - Breakout session A', 'Day 2 - Breakout session B', 'Welcome Board | Starter Plan', and 'Workshop Landing Board'. A purple circle highlights the first three breakout sessions. An inset window shows a detailed view of 'Day 1 - Breakout session 1', which is divided into four columns: 'THE QUESTIONS', 'THE LANDSCAPE', 'Q1 Do you agree or disagree with the aspects of the current landscape and why?', and 'Other comments'. The 'THE QUESTIONS' column contains three questions. The 'THE LANDSCAPE' column features a flowchart. The 'Q1' column contains several orange sticky notes. The 'Other comments' column contains yellow sticky notes. A purple box highlights a specific sticky note in the 'Q1' column with the text: 'EXAMPLE To have more open access publications of protocols: if these were acknowledged as publications on a resume they are not likely to be published'. A purple arrow points from this note to the 'THE QUESTIONS' column in the main board view.

You can change rooms in the “Breakout rooms” icon (may be in “More” for narrow screens).
May not be possible for day 1

Now open the **README** in the w/s drive

<https://tinyurl.com/y6razjm7>

Day 2. Thursday, October 2025

14:00 - 18:00 CEST, online

14:00 - 14:30	<p>A recap of day 1 and outline of day 2 Katrina Exter (VLIZ) How to use the Miro boards today Emilie Boulanger (UNESCO)</p>
14:30 - 15:45 (includes coffee break)	<p>Breakout Sessions A Data publishers (DNA and biodiversity) lead by Katrina Exter (VLIZ) and Christina Pavlouli (EMBRC) B Reference libraries, Bioinformatics, Taxonomies (data) lead by Emilie Boulanger and Saara Suominen (UNESCO) C Biobanks, Culture collections, Taxonomies (concepts) lead by Pascal Hablutzel (VLIZ) and Seascope Belgium Attendees can select their own groups Attendees can take breaks as and when they wish during the session</p>
15:45 - 16:15	<p>Plenary: summary of the breakouts</p>
16:15 - 17:30 (includes coffee break)	<p>Breakout Sessions A Data publishers (DNA and biodiversity) lead by Katrina Exter (VLIZ) and Christina Pavlouli B Reference libraries, Bioinformatics, Taxonomies (data) lead by Emilie Boulanger and Saara Suominen (UNESCO) C Biobanks, Culture collections, Taxonomies (concepts) lead by Pascal Hablutzel (VLIZ) and Seascope Belgium Attendees can return to the previous group or select a new one Attendees can take breaks as and when they wish during the session</p>
17:30 - 18:00	<p>Plenary: summary of the breakouts. Workshop debrief and next steps</p>

<https://tinyurl.com/bdd7rvef>

A selected summary of Day 1

- There is a need for a **map of the eDNA digital ecosystem** for data creators who want to publish their data (reduce confusion and frustration!)
- There is a need for a **best practices when publishing (different types of) data** for data creators – aimed both at those who work in (e)DNA *and* those who are not DNA experts (e.g. monitoring scientists). Ideally should be endorsed by the relevant stakeholders
- Creating **automated (meta)data sharing** between stakeholders (using web-tech) will clearly make for a smoother ecosystem and solve many problems....
-but we have to **consider those regions with fewer resources and less data-IT expertise**. Can we find a way to share solutions and transfer knowledge?
- **Data literacy and having the mindset to publish (and open access to) data** is still a big stumbling block (among data creators and some data providers both!): how can we carrot-and-stick Europe (let alone the rest of the world) into improving this? Require and Credit!

A selected summary of Day 1

- We all agree that **quality, commonality, and completeness of meta/data** (both catalogue metadata and that within data) is important and needs improving (going forward and for “historical” data); this requires work from all the stakeholders in this ecosystem and should be better coordinated than it is at present
- Those of us at this w/s may want to **join forces** in doing/looking at/experting on topics we have identified as being necessary to the digital ecosystem but which are under stress at present: if it is linked only to one project it is less sustainable. Sign-up sheet?

